

Applying Distributed Ledger Technologies for Trusted and Secure Network Topology Management in Multi-Stakeholder Environments: A Case Study from the ADRENALINE Testbed

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Abstract—The increasingly interconnected nature of modern network architectures demands advanced security and trust mechanisms, particularly in environments spanning multiple technology and stakeholder domains. Traditional approaches to network management systems, while effective in static settings, often lack the flexibility, security, and transparency required for dynamic and decentralized operations typical of multi-domain configurations. Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT) offer a robust alternative by enabling decentralized management and immutable recording of network configurations, inherently increasing security against tampering and unauthorized changes. This paper introduces a DLT approach utilizing a private, permissioned ledger where topology changes are recorded as transactions. The setup enforces data integrity and restricts access to network topology information, ensuring only authorized stakeholders can make changes. Consequently, it enhances security, maintains data consistency, and builds trust among network components by keeping a verifiable record of all changes. Additionally, the paper examines the performance and operational efficiency of integrating DLT within network systems, using the ADRENALINE testbed—an advanced infrastructure for Beyond 5G and future 6G services—as the platform for analysis. Experimental results reveal the system’s performance metrics, illustrating the practical viability of implementing DLT in network operations management.

Index Terms—DLT, Hyperledger Fabric, Network Topology Management, Multi-Domain Networks, ADRENALINE Testbed

I. INTRODUCTION

The evolution of networking systems has transformed traditional network management concepts. Historically, network management was limited to physical locations, such as company data centers or office buildings, where centralized control systems were practical and effective. However, advancements in technologies such as Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) have revolutionized network management by decoupling the control plane from the data plane and enabling dynamic, flexible, and scalable network operations [1]. These technologies have led to the deployment of multi-controller environments, where each controller is responsible for a specific technology domain, such as optical or IP networks.

As these technologies advanced, the role of network orchestrators became crucial. They oversee the operations of

various network components and ensure seamless integration and coordination across different stakeholder domains. Orchestrators facilitate top-down management of resources and services by providing an abstract view of the network [2]. This hierarchical management structure is essential for maintaining the efficiency and reliability of complex network systems, such as operator administrative domains.

However, several challenges arise as networking systems become complex and involve multiple stakeholders. Sharing information required for network management across different domains becomes increasingly difficult, particularly in maintaining consistency, security, and privacy. Additionally, authorization and authentication constraints become more pronounced as the number of stakeholders and the volume of sensitive information increase [3]. Ensuring that only authorized entities can access specific data while preventing unauthorized access is a significant challenge. Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT), such as blockchain, offers a promising solution to these challenges. Specifically, permissioned blockchains can provide a secure, decentralized framework for managing and sharing information. Unlike public blockchains, permissioned blockchains restrict access to authorized participants, ensuring privacy and controlled access to the ledger’s records [4]. The immutable nature of blockchain ensures that once data is recorded, it cannot be altered or deleted, guaranteeing data integrity and transparency among stakeholders.

This paper presents a blockchain-based method for securely storing and sharing network topology information for network management decisions. We leverage Hyperledger Fabric, a permissioned blockchain framework, to create a secure ledger that records topology changes as transactions. This ledger is accessible only to three key stakeholders within the same administrative domain: an End-to-End (E2E) SDN Orchestrator, an IP-SDN Controller, and an Optical-SDN Controller, ensuring they can access and update the network topology information relevant to their roles. To validate the effectiveness and practical applicability of our approach, we evaluate it within the ADRENALINE testbed—an advanced network infrastructure developed for Beyond 5G and 6G services.

The main contributions of this work are: a) the introduction

of a blockchain-based approach for secure network topology management that decentralizes information control, mitigating the risks of data tampering and unauthorized access; b) validation of the proposed approach within the ADRENALINE testbed, showcasing its practical applicability and effectiveness; and c) evaluation of the performance implications of integrating blockchain technology into network management systems, providing insights into operational efficiency.

The paper is organized as follows: Section II presents related work with relevant studies concerning blockchain and network management. Section III describes the proposed system in detail. Section IV discusses the experimental setup and performance results. Finally, Section V concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

Blockchain technology has been increasingly adopted in various network management domains due to its potential to enhance security, transparency, and trust. The authors in [5] evaluated the abstraction of optical topology models in blockchain-based data center interconnections. An SDN architecture integrating blockchain enabled each optical transport operator domain to become a peer in a blockchain network, using three abstraction models to manage resources and deploy connectivity services. The study concluded that blockchain provides a robust mechanism for managing optical transport domains by ensuring spectrum continuity and sharing resources in a controlled and immutable manner. This approach can potentially benefit other technology domains in more complex systems, providing a foundation for further research.

In [6], the authors explored blockchain technology to enhance the security of Zero-touch Service Management (ZSM) frameworks. They defined a multi-domain network infrastructure adopting the ZSM approach and integrating blockchain functionality. The study highlighted blockchain's significant advantages over traditional databases due to its decentralized structure, immutable records, and enhanced security. The authors also explored different DLTs to meet ZSM security needs and provided guidelines for prospective solution designers. However, the study lacked actual implementation and performance results, which are crucial for evaluating practical viability.

The authors in [7] reviewed ZSM for 5G and beyond networks, emphasizing blockchain technology's potential to enhance security and trust. They highlighted benefits such as decentralized trust, data integrity, enhanced security, automation through smart contracts, and improved interoperability and scalability. Decentralization is crucial for establishing trust in a multi-stakeholder environment, where various network providers must collaborate without fully trusting each other. By implementing a private, permissioned blockchain network, the ZSM framework can ensure that only authorized entities participate, thereby reducing the risk of malicious actors infiltrating the system. Furthermore, blockchain ensures that all transactions, including network management functions and AI/ML decisions, are immutably recorded. Despite the substantial theoretical benefits, actual implementations are still

few, indicating a need for further research to explore practical applications and evaluate performance in real-world scenarios.

In [8], the authors proposed a blockchain-empowered framework for decentralized network management in 6G mobile networks. The framework addressed spectrum and infrastructure sharing among multiple mobile network operators, leveraging blockchain's decentralization to eliminate central authority, enhance security through cryptographic hashing and consensus mechanisms, and ensure transparency by immutably recording transactions. While the study provided simulation details showcasing the framework's potential, the actual integration of blockchain in 6G networks must consider the evolving nature of 6G technology and practical deployment requirements.

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed integration of DLT with the ADRENALINE testbed aims to enhance the security, transparency, and trustworthiness of network topology management across multiple stakeholder domains. Our proposed model, depicted in Fig. 1, integrates DLT with nodes distributed among the controllers: the IP SDN Controller, the Optical SDN Controller, and the E2E SDN Orchestrator.

A. ADRENALINE Testbed Overview

The ADRENALINE testbed is an open and disaggregated SDN/NFV-enabled packet/optical transport network and edge/cloud computing infrastructure designed for Beyond 5G, future 6G, and IoT/V2X services. It encompasses several network segments, including the edge/access and metro networks, integrating advanced network technologies to provide a flexible and scalable infrastructure. The testbed features a partially disaggregated optical network functioning as the metro network, comprising a photonic mesh network with Reconfigurable Optical Add-Drop Multiplexer (ROADMs) and bidirectional Dense Wavelength-Division Multiplexing (DWDM) amplified optical links and a Spatial Division Multiplexing (SDM) domain with Spatial Cross Connect devices (SXC) connected by multi-core fiber. It includes packet optical nodes with 400G data rate transponders for transporting traffic flows between the access and metro network segments. IP Cell Site Gateways (CSGs) represent heterogeneous access network technologies with Edge DC capacities and connections using 100G QSFP28 interfaces. The ADRENALINE testbed is managed by dedicated TeraFlowSDN [9] controllers for each technological domain (e.g., IP, optical) and coordinated hierarchically through an E2E TeraFlowSDN Orchestrator, supporting seamless end-to-end connectivity and efficient resource orchestration across diverse network segments.

B. Integration with DLT

In the proposed methodology, DLT guarantees the integrity and security of topology management operations within the ADRENALINE network. This approach leverages smart contracts to implement the chaincode logic for operations such as STORE, UPDATE, FETCH, and DELETE topology information. Utilizing a permissioned blockchain framework such

Fig. 1. Proposed model integrating DLT with the ADRENALINE Testbed

as Hyperledger Fabric ensures that only entities with the appropriate access rights can interact with the chaincode and perform these operations. Hyperledger Fabric’s Membership Service Provider (MSP) manages identities and access control to authenticate and authorize participants.

The decentralized nature of the blockchain distributes the storage and operations regarding network topology information across multiple peer nodes, eliminating single points of failure and ensuring resilience. Channels provide isolated environments for transactions, ensuring privacy and data integrity by allowing only authorized participants to access specific ledgers. The world state database maintains the current value of the ledger’s data, ensuring the most recent network topology information is readily available for all authorized participants.

The DLT integration for topology management is depicted in the sequence diagram shown in Fig. 2. Initially, the IP SDN Controller and Optical SDN Controller store their respective topologies by sending `STORE` requests as transaction proposals to their corresponding peer nodes which endorse the transactions and forward validated transactions to the Orderer. The Orderer delivers a block containing the ordered transactions back to the peer nodes, which record the topologies in the DLT Ledger and confirm the operation to the controllers. Subsequently, the E2E SDN Orchestrator sends `FETCH` operations to retrieve the IP and optical topologies by querying the peer nodes, which query the DLT Ledger and return the topology information. The E2E SDN Orchestrator then computes the end-to-end topology and `STORES` this aggregated information

in the ledger, sending a transaction to the blockchain, recording the data, and confirming the operation.

IV. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS

The experimental setup was configured as illustrated in Fig. 3. A Hyperledger Fabric v2.5 deployment was prepared on three Ubuntu 22.04 machines housing the E2E SDN Orchestrator (*E2E_TFS*), Optical SDN Controller (*Optical_TFS*), and IP SDN Controller (*IP_TFS*) with full network visibility between each other. The deployment was configured with one *orderer* node and three *peer* nodes. The *orderer* and *peer1* nodes were positioned in the *E2E_TFS* machine, while *peer2* and *peer3* were positioned in *Optical_TFS* and *IP_TFS* respectively. The Hyperledger Fabric components were deployed as Docker containers with networking managed directly by a configured Docker network. Host naming was configured on each machine for domain name resolution.

The chaincode logic for the proposed experimental scenario was coded in Golang with functions for `STORE`, `UPDATE`, `FETCH`, and `DELETE` operations on network topology data. A single channel and organization were configured for the deployment, with all nodes belonging to the same organization. Consequently, the chaincode was installed and activated on all the peer nodes so they could endorse transactions.

Four topologies that are part of the ADRENALINE testbed were utilized for the experiments. The topologies are JSON files with *key* pairs for *devices* and *links* alongside a *topology_id*. The sizes of the JSON files in kilobytes are as follows:

Fig. 2. Topology management DLT operations

topo_dc with 5KB, *topo_ip* with 16KB, *topo_e2e* with 18KB, and *topo_optical* with 10KB.

The methodology for the results considered a test scenario in which a Node.js application writes and fetches topology information from the blockchain. The codification of the Node.js application follows the guidelines of *release-2.5* of

Hyperledger Fabric, where interaction with the chaincode is achieved by the gRPC class to the Fabric Gateway API that exists on the peer nodes.

The performance of the chaincode operations was evaluated by running the Node.js application and executing each operation 1000 times for a given topology. Fig. 4 showcases the performance results as a histogram condensing the chaincode operations for every topology. The operations with the higher execution times are those that write/change the state of the ledger, while the operations that query the blockchain are executed almost instantly. Despite the variation in the size of each topology, there was not enough variation in execution time for each operation.

Fig. 5 presents the Cumulative Distribution Function (CDF) of the execution times for each chaincode operation within the topology *topo_e2e*. This topology was selected as the size of the JSON file was the largest. The CDF plot clearly shows that the operations exhibit distinct clusters of execution times along the x-axis. Operations that query the blockchain, such as `FETCH`, are represented in green and demonstrate very low execution times, clustering near the origin of the x-axis. This indicates that these operations are consistently completed very quickly with minimal variability. Conversely, operations that modify the ledger state, such as `STORE`, `UPDATE`, and `DELETE`, exhibit higher execution times. A significant proportion of these operations are completed within the range of approximately 2000 to 2500 ms. This behavior is due to the RAFT consensus mechanism in Hyperledger Fabric, where a batch window waits for several transactions to fill the block. As these transactions are sent in isolation, the block has to wait for the full window to be committed.

To illustrate the impact of the execution times in mimicking a realistic operation, a throughput test was carried out. During the test, 1000 `STORE` operations were executed at different transactions per second (TPS) rates for 10TPS, 50TPS, 250TPS, and 500TPS. After execution, the real throughput of the operations was recorded. As showcased in Fig. 6,

Fig. 3. DLT experiments configuration.

Fig. 4. Execution time for each operation for all the topologies

Fig. 5. CDF of the blockchain operations using topo_e2e

the execution times significantly influenced the real TPS. At lower TPS rates, the system managed to maintain throughput close to the expected values, indicating efficient handling of operations with minimal delays. However, as the TPS rate increased, the real throughput diverged from the expected values, highlighting the system’s struggle to maintain the higher load. This divergence is particularly pronounced at 500 TPS.

Optimizing the execution times for state-changing operations is crucial for maintaining high performance, especially under heavy transactional loads. This can be achieved by carefully tuning the Hyperledger Fabric block configuration, namely the `BatchTimeout` and `BatchSize`, to adjust it to the needs of the expected operation of the system.

V. CONCLUSION

This paper proposed a method for securely managing and sharing network topology information within the ADRENALINE testbed using DLT. By leveraging a permissioned blockchain framework like Hyperledger Fabric, the

Fig. 6. Transaction throughput for the STORE operation - topo_e2e

methodology aims to maintain the integrity and transparency of operations across multiple stakeholders. Smart contracts were employed to automate storing, updating, fetching, and deleting topology information, providing a decentralized and immutable record of network configurations.

While promising, this approach presents challenges, such as potential performance overhead due to the consensus mechanisms and transaction processing inherent in blockchain networks. Future research should optimize these aspects by tuning the configuration of Hyperledger, exploring alternative consensus mechanisms, and integrating distributed databases such as the InterPlanetary File System (IPFS) to minimize the storage of information inside the blockchain. Conducting extensive real-world testing in diverse network environments will also be crucial.

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